

Disclosure of the Alien Technology & Modern Science on Earth

By a researcher for @GlobalDisclosure (YouTube)

Abstract: Our modern science and technology are the result of at least 2 major events of alien contact on earth, namely, the Industrial Revolution and the Roswell UFO incident. I will disclose further details of the timeline and outline in this paper.

Our modern science and technology are derived primarily from 2 important events, which preceded other notable events, in history. Firstly, the Industrial Revolution in the 18th century. And secondly, the Roswell UFO incident, since 1947. The retrieval of craft and EBE in the Roswell UFO incident eventually proceeded to events mentioned in the declassified “*Project Serpo*” of America. The Industrial Revolution coincides with the beginning of the crop circles in England, UK of Great Britain. Aliens (also referred to, as EBE) are amongst those that introduced engineering and modern science & technology to humans, which eventually include engines, vehicles of sea, land, air & space, industrial machinery, DNA & genetic science, nanotechnology, satellites, telescopes, nuclear energy, explosives, designer chemicals, detection of the electromagnetic spectrum, robotics, CPU & GPU, digital cryptography, smartphones, telegraphy, wireless technology, so on and so forth. The terms, ‘scientist’ and ‘engineer’, originated from the Industrial Revolution.

The “*Freemasonry*” (*Freemason* is a public-fronted term), amongst others, received the said alien technology since the 18th century. In the Roswell UFO incident of 1947, the technology of semiconductor was obtained. Other groups, such as the Vatican and royal families, also might have obtained alien technology, or part of it.

The mentioned quoted terms “*Freemasonry*”, “*Project Serpo*” and “*Project Blue Beam*”, are subjects that have not been fully explored by, or disclosed to the general public currently. The *Table* and *Figures* below supplement the outline of this article.

Date	Event	Result (With Origins & Inventions)
18 th century	Industrial Revolution	Crop circles, start of modern science, <i>engineering</i> , construction & masonry, electricity, telegraphy, industrial machinery
1947	Roswell UFO	Retrieved UFO craft, alien (EBE) specimens, <i>semiconductor</i> , computer technology
After 1947	"Project Serpo"	Smartphones, wireless technology, <i>DNA & bio-engineering</i> , quantum physics, HAARP
21 th century	<i>Disclosures</i>	Advanced satellites & rockets, UAP, declassification, " <i>Project Blue Beam</i> "

Table 1. Outlined summary of events resulting in modern science, technology & engineering.

Diffusion of the Industrial Revolution

Figure 1. Source and dispersion of the Industrial Revolution.

Figure 2. Maps of the industries in England after the Industrial Revolution.

Figure 3. Locations of crop circles in England, 2002.

Figure no. 1, 2 and 3; show that crop circles, as well as alien contacts, are related to the beginning of the Industrial Revolution. Hence, the royal families (political elites) which hold information of alien technology, as well as the ancestry of American political powers, likely originated in England.

Reference & Resource

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